

Effect of Valency State of Vanadium on Stereoblock Polymerization of Methyl Methacrylate with Ziegler-Natta Catalyst Systems.*

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The valency state of transition metal in Ziegler-Natta catalyst has great influence on yield, stereo regularity and molecular weight of the polymer obtained. The Al/V ratio and structure of aluminium alkyls determine the valency of vanadium in an active catalyst complex.

In order to examine the effect of valency state of vanadium on catalyst activity and stereospecificity, a detailed kinetic study with Ziegler-Natta catalyst systems comprising of vanadium halides and aluminium alkyls has been carried out.

The first-order dependence of rate of polymerization on catalyst and monomer concentrations, and activation energies of 9.2 and 6.6 Kcal/mole respectively for VOCl_2 - AlEt_2Cl and VOCl_2 - AlEt_2Br catalyst systems, suggest co-ordinate anionic mechanism of polymerization.

Many investigators have assigned (V^{+3}) to (V^{+5}) as a formal oxidation state for vanadium present in polymerization catalyst complex. Our studies show that catalyst containing (V^{+3}) is less active than (V^{+5}). Vanadium in still higher oxidation state ($>\text{V}^{+3}$) is inactive for polymerization of methyl methacrylate. It was also observed that (V^{+3}) active sites are preferred for isotactic and (V^{+5}) active sites for syndiotactic poly-methyl methacrylate formation.

THE classical Ziegler-Natta catalyst consisting of TiCl_4 - $\text{Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_3$ was assumed to be inactivated by polar monomers¹. As a result, stereoregular polymers of polar monomers were considered a remote possibility. Earlier work²⁻⁴ carried out at our laboratory and also by several other workers has shown in general, that vanadium based Ziegler-Natta catalyst systems are more effective than titanium containing catalysts for polymerization of polar monomer such as methyl methacrylate.

Valency of transition metal is an important factor determining the activity and selectivity of catalyst. The variation of valency of transition metal on mixing with different types of aluminium alkyls has been the subject of considerable study⁵⁻⁶. Many investigators have assigned V^{+3} to V^{+5} as a formal oxidation state for vanadium present in catalyst complex⁷⁻¹⁴.

In this paper results of our studies on polymerization of methyl methacrylate with vanadium containing Ziegler-Natta catalyst system¹⁵⁻¹⁷ are reported. The effect of valency state of vanadium on catalyst activity, stereoregularity and molecular weight of polymer is discussed.

Experimental

Atmospheric oxygen and traces of moisture have very adverse effect on transition metal halides, organometallic compounds and their reaction products.

Therefore all the reagents, solvents and monomer were purified, distilled and stored under nitrogen atmosphere. The preparations of catalyst solutions and their mixing were carried out inside a dry glove box made of wood. The order of addition of reagents was strictly followed as reported in earlier publication³. The polymerization was conducted in closed conditions at constant temperature in a thermostat. The polymers were precipitated in a large excess of acidic methanol, filtered and dried under vacuum.

Vanadium oxychloride was prepared by reacting 1 mole of V_2O_5 with 2 moles of anhydrous AlCl_3 at about 400° and distilled out as a brown liquid. On redistillation under anhydrous conditions a lemon yellow liquid was obtained.

Vanadium tetrachloride (Stauffer Chemical Co., U.S.A.) was distilled under inert conditions before use. Fresh solutions (0.5 M) of VOCl_3 and VCl_4 in n-hexane were made every 4-5 days from freshly distilled VOCl_3 and VCl_4 , because dark brown solid started depositing on walls of container on further storage.

$\text{Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Cl}$ (Poly olefins, Bombay) and $\text{Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Br}$ prepared by reaction of magnaluminium (Al_2Mg) with ethyl bromide, were distilled in nitrogen atmosphere under reduced pressure and stored under inert atmosphere.

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NMR spectra were recorded with the varian A-60 MCPS spectrophotometer in 3% (W/V) chloroform solution at 25°. Intrinsic viscosities of polymer obtained were determined in chloroform at 30° and viscosity average molecular weights were calculated by the relationship¹⁸

$$\eta = 4.3 \times 10^{-5} M^{0.5}$$

Results and Discussion

It is well-known that after mixing vanadium halide and aluminium alkyl dark brown precipitate is formed. The colour of the precipitate remains unchanged after addition of monomer, showing presence of undisturbed catalyst complex.

The reduction of vanadium depends on Al/V ratio and type of aluminium alkyls used⁶. It is known that average valency of vanadium decreases as the Al/V ratio increases¹⁹. Therefore in order to see the effect of valency state of vanadium and determine the ratios of optimum activity, Al/V ratio was varied from 1 to 8. It was observed that the catalytic activity was maximum at ratios Al/V=2 and 7 (Fig. 1) for $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Cl}$ catalyst system and Al/V=4 and 8 (Fig. 2) for $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Br}$ catalyst system.

Fig. 1. Effect of Al/V ratio on $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-AlEt}_2\text{Cl}$ system.

Table (1) shows the comparison of vanadium based catalyst systems for polymerization of methyl methacrylate under identical conditions of polymerizations. It is clear from table 1 that $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Cl}$ is five times more active than that of $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Br}$ and $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Br}$ catalyst systems.

Fig. 2

Fig. 2. Effect of Al/V ratio on $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-AlEt}_2\text{Br}$ system.

Natta's study²⁰ for polymerization of propylene showed that $\text{VCl}_3\text{-Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Cl}$ catalyst system is more active than $\text{VCl}_3\text{-Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Br}$ catalyst system and he found that there is no V^{+2} in $\text{VCl}_3\text{-Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Br}$ catalyst system. The average valence of vanadium³ in the catalyst complex formed with $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Br}$ and $\text{Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Cl}$ is 3. Thus it shows that vanadium in $+3$ oxidation state is more active. The less activity of $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-Al}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_5)_2\text{Br}$ may be due to presence of more V^{+2} than V^{+3} because of reduction at higher ratio of Al/V = 4 and long time of aging of catalyst¹⁰⁻¹⁹.

Cossee's theory¹⁰ of catalytic polymerization activity includes V^{+2} oxidation state for vanadium, because it allows for activity in transition metal ions with three unpaired electrons. De Liefde Meijer *et al*^{11,12} looked at similar catalysts and concluded that V^{+2} or V^{+3} could be active species. Recently¹⁴ even V^{+4} and V^{+5} oxidation states of vanadium have been suggested to possess catalytic activity. But in our studies⁷ it was found that vanadium in higher oxidation state (V^{+3}) is inactive for polymerization of methyl methacrylate.

Recently Svab *et al*²¹ studied the catalytic efficiency of VOCl_3 and VCl_4 with aluminium alkyls for polymerization of propylene and they found that syndiotactic index increased with increasing % V^{+3} in catalyst. Similarly from our studies of NMR spectra (Fig. 3) of polymethyl methacrylate obtained with different catalyst systems, it is clear that the percentage of syndiotactic units (Table 1) is more for V^{+3} oxidation state, which directly suggests that V^{+3} oxidation state is favoured for syndiotactic polymethyl methacrylate and V^{+2} oxidation state for isotactic polymethyl methacrylate formation.

The molecular weights (Table 1) of polymers lie in the range of 60,000 to 70,000, which shows that molecular weights do not change with change in oxidation state of vanadium in catalyst complex.

TABLE-1
COMPARISON OF CATALYST SYSTEMS

Catalyst system	Percentage conversion	Rate constants L/M/S		Percentage of syndiotactic, heterotactic and isotactic units from NMR spectra			Mol. Wt.
		w.r.t. catalyst	w.r.t monomer	S 9.14 ; ppm	H 8.98 ; ppm	I 8.78 ; ppm	
(1) $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-AlEt}_3$	4.58	5.61×10^{-5}	4.63×10^{-5}	41	29	30	—
(2) $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-AlEt}_2\text{Cl}$	19.29	23.21×10^{-5}	12.79×10^{-5}	47	38	15	61.000
(3) $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-AlEt}_2\text{Br}^*$	4.57	9.30×10^{-5}	9.04×10^{-5}	32	31	37	69.000

Al/V ratio = 2 Aging time = 20 min. Catalyst = 0.05 mole/l
 Temperature = 40°C Reaction time = 180 min. NMA = 1.88 mole/l

*In case of $\text{VOCl}_3\text{-AlEt}_2\text{Br}$:

Al/V ratio = 4 Aging time = 24 hrs.

Fig. 3. Nuclear Magnetic Resonance Spectra of PMMA.

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